

EDUCATIONAL KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

13.

Pilot Guide

Project Information

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1. EKT PROJECT BACKGROUND

The Education Knowledge Transfer (EKT) project brings together 11 institutions and organisations from Austria, Belgium, Ireland, Portugal, Spain and the UK. This consortium has many years of experience in both educational and technological innovation and teacher training. EKT was set up with the aim of enhancing in-school placement experience through the development and testing of innovative methodologies and bespoke eLearning solutions. The project is funded through the Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliance for Higher Education Programme.

The EKT Project Consortium strongly believes that it is crucial for the future teachers to experience a real, classroom contexts to help them confirm their choice of profession and support their self-reflection. The EKT project is developing tools and strategies to support university-school collaboration, which is a key element in Initial Teacher Education (ITE). This is fundamental in early career support for teachers as stated by the European Commission (2012, COM/2012/0669, Council conclusions on effective teacher education, OJ C 183, 14.06.2014).

The in-school placement process that includes the participation of university lecturers and non-university teaching mentors can have a strategic impact in the training of student teachers and sets a favourable scenario to promote the interaction between theory and practice, exercise professional skills and experiment proposals for educational innovation monitored by experienced professionals and analysed by educational researchers. The EKT consortium has set out to improve the in-school placement process to meet the needs of teachers entering the world of work as well as the needs of future schools. The consortium believes that the improvement can be implemented through the application of resources and services, delivered through e-learning methods.

The EKT Project is supporting and improving the school placement experience of Student Teachers by providing them with a methodology framework and an innovative online platform and e-learning solutions that allows collaboration and communication among all actors/stakeholders involved in the school placement programme.

The EKT project brings together education, the technology industry, the dynamics of scientific knowledge production and knowledge transfer, to pursue **two main objectives**:

- To improve the **quality of Initial Teacher Education** (ITE) and support during in-school placement
- To develop **e-learning methodologies** and solutions which will facilitate more effective communication and support during in-school placement.

The e-learning methodologies and solutions being developed in the EKT project are designed to promote dynamics of coordinated work between the university and non-university teachers who supervise and accompany the student during the in-school placement experience.

Figure 1: EKT draws from the strategic triangle of schools, technology sector and universities.

This can enable the University to provide individualized follow-up of students while in-school placement practice and encourage self-learning and reflective thinking that the future teacher must perform during the period of teaching practice.

International trends and scientific literature reinforce the importance of in-service placements and the need for the first years of the profession (a period of initiation to the profession) to become a high-quality training experience.

We believe that the results of this project can be useful and can be transferred not only to ITE but to the new systems of access to the teaching profession that can be implemented in Europe in the coming years.

Figure 2: EKT knowledge development to enhance the in-school placement experience is based on teaching innovation, educational research and technological development.

2. EKT PILOT

2.1. Aim of the EKT Pilot Testing

The EKT pilot is the key activity of the project where universities in five countries (Spain, England, Austria, Ireland and Portugal) will apply the EKT methodology and the e-learning system in the development of the in-school teaching practices of the Student Teachers of the five Faculties / Colleges of Education.

The **five university institutions in the EKT consortium participating** in the EKT pilot are:

- Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain)
- Pädagogische Hochschule Wien (Austria)
- Marino Institute of Education (Ireland)
- Universidade do Minho (Portugal)
- University of Plymouth (UK)

Partner universities will embed the EKT methodology and resources into their existing teaching programmes, and will engage all relevant stakeholders i.e. Academic Mentors, School Mentors, University and School Coordinators, and Student Teachers.

The pilot testing phase will help provide crucial information about the methodology, platform, resources, and online training and will inform the final design. The advantage of the pilot testing is that it will enable project partners to see what works well for the target audience and which methods and approaches are appropriate.

This pilot testing will provide information that will enable decision to be made regarding the final design of the EKT learning platform and online tutorials.

This document aims to provide guidance on the process, tasks and responsibilities for each participant of the pilot implementation phase. This is to ensure that a common path is followed in each pilot organization. However, **it is expected that each pilot implementation will be different as it should take into account the national rules, regulations and programme requirements.**

In principal, the EKT Pilot process has been divided into the following **three phases**:

- EKT Pilot Preparation
- EKT Pilot Implementation
- EKT Post Pilot Activities

Each phase includes a number of key activities but there is no strict cut-off point between them as some of them may overlap.

Two series of pilot testing are planned as part of the project with the 1st round scheduled for the Spring/Summer semester of 2022 and the 2nd round for Autumn semester of 2022. Each piloting university should make a detailed plan for their pilot that includes at least the information on:

- Departments involved in the EKT pilot
- No. & profile of University Mentors
- No. & profile of School Mentors
- No. & profile of Student Teachers
- Preferred SPOC Period
- Preferred period of Pilot Implementation

3. EKT METHODOLOGY

The EKT Methodology is one of the first key intellectual outputs of the project and worked as the pedagogical and technological framework for the transformation and improvement of the in-school placement process and practices. The methodology has been developed based on the expertise and experience of the project partners but also a needs analysis study that has been carried out with teachers in the participating countries (Austria, Ireland, Portugal, Spain, the UK). **The EKT methodology is an important document as it:**

- Provides a shared vision of the model the teacher we want to train and the role that in-school placement plays in the initial teacher training process.
- Defines the specifications and functionalities for the design and development of the EKT e-learning system for the in-school placement.
- Provides a flexible methodological framework (objectives, sequence, instruments) which, based on the EKT technological system, allows the adaptation of In-school placement strategies of initial training institutions, European participants, innovation and testing of the system.

It therefore does not propose a fixed or single route to follow, but rather provides institutions and those responsible for European In-School placement with a framework (guidance and tools) on the basis of which the two mentors (academic and school) design and negotiate a personalised practice plan for each prospective teacher and implement it with the support of their educational communities.

The EKT methodology does not constitute a fixed route for developing In-school placement in all initial training institutions in Europe. It provides a coherent and flexible framework on which to build and rethink the practice models and strategies of initial training institutions and the roles of their protagonists (mentors and future teachers).

Collaboration and coordination of work between universities and schools in preparation and during the placement period is one of the two key dimensions of the EKT methodology and pilot.

The coordination during the in-school placement aims to ensure that the process is developed by accompanying the student at all times (preparation, development and closure phases of the in-school placement) and advising him/her in a collaborative manner and with shared responsibility (both academic and school mentors).

The main focus of the EKT Methodology is to provide a process for the Academic Mentor and School Mentor to actively support the Student Teacher throughout their in-school placement. The methodology is designed to assess and strengthen the student's individual and reflective learning. The student will use the ePortfolio as a training tool to record, write down, incorporate training materials and materials for their in-school placement. The student also has the flexibility to add elements to the structure and all the issues or sections, which are the reflection of what the student is learning.

A summary video of the EKT Methodology can be watched here: <https://youtu.be/Fe9OrY2E9IU>

Full description of the EKT Methodology (Educational and Technological Framework) can be read in the EKT site <https://ektproject.eu/resources> (Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro, B. & Trigo Miranda (2023). Technological framework for development of professional competences in in-school placement. EKT Output 6. Santiago de Compostela: University of Santiago de Compostela.)

The EKT platform is an e-learning solution that has been designed to support pre-service teachers during their in-school placement and support and strengthen communication and collaboration between Academic and School Mentors and other actors involved in the school placement programme. It has been developed by the technical partners of the EKT project in close collaboration with the academic partners who provided inputs to the platform specification and functionality.

The user-centered design of the EKT solution makes all the apps available from a unique entry point based on Single Sign On technology, allowing the student, teacher or mentor to access all needed tools together from one single dashboard.

This section provides a list of the available features and functions within the EKT platform that are available to its users.

4. EKT PLATFORM

4.1. Registration and login

The University Coordinator is responsible for setting up the University on the EKT Platform and registering the Academic Mentors, Student Teachers, School Mentors and to login to the system, the user goes to:

app.ektproject.eu

Figure 5: EKT Login page and URL

4.2. Main features and functions

4.2.1. EKT Dashboard

Once the user is logged in, they will see the EKT Dashboard. This landing page provides access to the main functions and sections of the EKT platform. The EKT dashboard has been updated with a new look for the 2nd round of pilot in Autumn 2022.

Figure 6: EKT Platform Dashboard

4.2.2. Management

Depending on the user profile this page displays different information for and about the platform users. It contains the list and number of students, groups, admins, coordinators and mentors, contact information, in relation with university/schools, courses.

In this section, in “My profile” users can view their profile information, change password, add picture, etc.

Academic Mentors or University School Placement Coordinators can:

- Create and manage accounts for new users (Students, School Mentors etc.).
- Create new courses to the platform, list the created courses, list the enrolled courses, etc.

4.2.3. Calendar

The calendar feature allows users add, edit, remove their own appointments. It gives possibility to share appointments with concrete users or with groups (depending on the role). Videoconference rooms can be linked to calendar events. Possibility to add reminders and also to set repetition on certain appointments.

4.2.4. Documents

The file and folder management and sharing feature allows users to create their own private files and folders (2GB), share folders between users on demand, share automated group folders depending on the role and edit files (word, excel, etc.) online and collaboratively. This is very similar to Google Docs or Microsoft OneDrive. Users can carry out the following:

- Access your files with the Nextcloud Web interface and create, preview, edit, delete, share, and re-share files.
- Upload or create new files or folders directly in a Nextcloud folder by clicking on the New button in the Files app.
- Share folders between users on demand. Automated group shared folders depending on the role.
- Edit files (word, excel, etc.) online and collaboratively.
- Assign tags to files. To create tags, open a file to the Details view. Then type your tags.
- Use the Details view to add and read comments on any file or folder. Comments are visible to everyone who has access to the file.

Figure 7: Details view

4.2.5. Communication

This platform feature allows participants to communicate with one or several users via chat or videoconference. The chat support both synchronous and asynchronous communication. Academic Mentors can create conversation groups. Share and embed documents from “my files” and include links to external documents within conversations. “Raise hand” within a videocall.

4.2.6. Training

The Training area provides content and activities for students and is provided through a Chamilo platform. University coordinators and mentors have the ability to create new courses and assign them to students. Students will only see the courses shared with them.

In each course the following tools will be available:

- **Course header:** The course header can customized with text, images and/or embedded videos.
- **Course description:** Describe the objectives of the course, outcomes, methodology, resources, assessment, etc.
- **Links:** Add web links relevant to the course, these can be external or internal sources if needed.
- **Learning Path:** This presents the structured content as a timeline. The mentor can choose the opening order elements of the timeline visible to the student. In this way, the student is led through the content and only sees the elements relevant to the stage of the course they are on. A learning path can contain multiple elements: files, tests, links, assignments, forums and files from the Contentcloud. The learning paths can be assigned to different students. It is also possible to view the results/progress of the students and also give them feedback.
- **Tests:** as a task or as evaluation method different tasks can be created and assign to different users. Tasks allow to user a huge type of questions. The test options include multiple choice, multiple answers, fill the blanks, matching, image zones, oral expression, multiple true/false, calculation questions, sequence, etc. As in the learning paths, the results/progress can be provided to students. The mentor can also provide individual feedback to students.

4.2.7. ePortfolio

A general eportfolio for the course in which all the students and all the mentors of the course can publish posts and comments but also every student has their own eportfolio in which he/she is the only one who can publish posts and the mentors and other students can access only to add comments instead of new entries. Each post is composed of a title, a content block (text, files, images, etc.) and tags to mark/categorize it. If a student considers a post on the public portfolio as valuable, they can add it to their own portfolio in order to work/reflect with it. The mentor can also send some post to other student own portfolio. Marks can be added at portfolio, post or comment levels.

4.2.8. Content Creation

Each EKT course has access to the content creation tool. This tool allows certain users to create different multimedia educational material. The contents are in xAPI format, this means that they can be exported.

4.2.9. Help Section

Users can find useful information on technical use of the platform and using the EKT system. The Help section contains tutorials, documentation, videos and an FAQ section. Users can use the contact forms to report platform errors or technical issues.

5. EKT ONLINE COURSE (SPOC)

The EKT Online Course has been developed as a Small Private Open Course (SPOC) to introduce and engage participants with the EKT Platform and to improve the school placement experience in line with the EKT methodology, thus focusing on the three areas:

- 1. The cooperation and collaboration between Academic Mentors and school cooperative teachers.**
- 2. The individualized follow-up of students in school placement.**
- 3. The reflective practice of Student Teachers.**

The SPOC intends to engage the participants with the EKT platform. The chosen approach is a mini self-study Action Research (action-oriented reflection) with a focus is on the question: 'How I can improve my practice?'

Participants will go through a structured process of reflection on-in-for practice. The tasks in the course are structured around the questions that aim to trigger participants' reflection and to engage the participants in discussions and dialogue with the others.

5.2.1. Key Outputs for Students

Students will work together with their Academic mentor and School Mentor to start their reflection on their teaching experience in the EKT e-portfolio and develop their Self-Study Action Research Plan.

During the pilot they are going to implement their Action Research plan and reflect on it during the school placement. At the end, they produce Action Research Report.

The key outputs of the EKT Online Course will be:

- **A Collaborative Document:** Checklist of Expectations for the In-School Placement around three areas: school engagements; professional engagements and teacher identity; and curriculum, teaching and learning – collaboratively compiled by the students, academic mentors and School Mentors (created collaboratively using the Communication Tool and uploaded in the Document Cloud).
- **Action Research Plan developed** by the Student Teachers with the support from academic mentors and School Mentors around the following points (posted in the ePortfolio):
 - A. Values around teaching and learning;
 - B. My Research Question/ Concern: framing the question and the reasons to choose this one;
- **What I Know About This Issue:**
 - A. Three valuable points I learned from the Literature Review.
 - B. Three valuable things I learned from Conversations with Colleagues.
 - C. A possible solution to my chosen issue / question / problem / concern.
 - D. Plan for gathering data and making sense of data (observations, collaborative reflection with Academic Mentors and School Mentors, ethical considerations).
- **Action Research Report** (Reflective Writing) – output of the Pilot, posted in the E-Portfolio.

The role of the **Academic Mentor** is to take part in discussions, to work with the School Mentor to support the students with theoretical knowledge in their inquiry, monitor the students' reflective posts and give constructive feedback using the EKT platform tools. Academic mentors evaluate the final Action Research Report.

The role of a **School Mentor** is to take part in discussions, to work with the Academic Mentor to support the students with practical advice in their inquiry, and give constructive feedback using the EKT platform tools.

Student engagement with the reflective journal and continuous support from academic mentors and School Mentors using the EKT e-Portfolio tool is seen as a key output for the EKT pilot.

Assessment in this online course is participatory mainly. This means that participation in discussions, feedback and responses to each other construct 50% of success in the course.

The key product to complete the course successfully Self-Study Action Research Plan, created by the Student Teacher in collaboration with the Academic Mentor and School Mentor.

The key product of the Pilot is Self-Study Action Research Report (Reflective Writing).

The full description of the SPOC content can be read in the EKT site <https://ektproject.eu/resources> (EKT Output 11. Training Contents for Teachers, Students and University Lecturers)

6. ROLES IN THE EKT PILOT

School placement is designed to give the Student Teacher an opportunity to learn about teaching and learning, to gain practice in teaching, to apply educational theory in a variety of teaching and learning situations and school contexts and to participate in school life in a way that is structured and supported. A number of stakeholders are involved in the process at both university and school levels; however, the roles and responsibilities may vary between countries involved in the pilot.

- University Coordinator
- Academic Mentor
- School Mentor
- School Coordinator
- Student Teacher

This section gives an overview of the roles of the various stakeholders within the EKT pilot.

6.1. Key Personnel at University Level

The University is responsible for leading the organisation of School Placement, including the supervision of students on school placement and communicating effectively with partner schools. Each of the EKT academic partners is responsible for making sure that the EKT pilot takes place and that specific in-school placement groups are identified, prepared to undergo the EKT methodology and provide feedback and data for the EKT Piloting report. The key personnel involved in the process at University level include:

6.1.1. University or College Coordinator

The University Coordinator is the person within the University who is responsible for coordinating and administering the school placement programme within the institution. This person is ensuring effective communication with students, university staff, partner schools and education providers involved in the school placement programme.

The University Coordinator is the single point of contact in each University who is overseeing the EKT Piloting process. Their role in the EKT pilot is to:

- Identify the student cohorts to participate in the EKT pilot in collaboration
- Create user accounts on the EKT platform for the pilot participants depending on their roles: Academic Mentor, School Mentor, School Coordinator and Student Teacher
- Assign the EKT platform users to relevant groups and courses
- Support colleagues to integrate the EKT methodology and platform into the in-school placement.
- Ensure that participating Academic Mentors and Student Teachers have undertaken the EKT SPOC prior to the EKT Pilot commencement.
- Assist in the evaluation of the EKT Methodology and EKT online platform.

6.1.2. Academic Mentor

The Academic Mentor is the person engaged by a University to support and mentor Student Teachers, support their teaching practice, and evaluate their practice while on in-school placement. The Academic Mentor monitors the Student Teacher's work and evaluates the final report.

The main tasks to be carried out by the Academic Mentor as part of the EKT pilot include:

- Participate in the EKT SPOC prior to the EKT Pilot commencement.
- Provide registration details for class groups, Students and School Mentors for set up on the EKT platform as required.
- Provide an EKT pilot plan in conjunction with the University Coordinator
- Prepare content on the EKT platform to compliment the in-school placement in line with the EKT methodology.
- Ensure that the Student Teacher is appropriately supported in all matters pertaining to the placement.
- Observe the Student Teacher teaching and provide constructive feedback using the EKT platform.
- Assist in the evaluation of the EKT Methodology and EKT online platform.

6.1.3. Student Teacher

The Student Teacher is the student who is undertaking a period of in-school placement as part of their initial teacher education. During the school placement the Student Teachers will work on improving their chosen area, while gathering evidence that their actions work or not. This requires observation, critical reflection and dialogue with the school tutor and Academic Mentor.

The main tasks to be carried out by the Student Teacher as part of the EKT pilot include include:

- Participate in the EKT SPOC prior to the EKT Pilot commencement
- Engage constructively and collaboratively in a broad range of professional experiences as part of the school placement process.
- Engage with constructive feedback from the Academic Mentors and School Mentor via the EKT platform
- Engage with other Student Teachers in the context of peer learning via the EKT platform communication tools
- Respond to the EKT evaluation surveys before and after the in-school placement and contribute to reflection activities where relevant

6.2. Key Personnel at School Level

School placement is designed to give the Student Teacher an opportunity to experience teaching and learning in a real environment, to apply educational theory in a variety of teaching and learning situations and school contexts, and to participate in school life in a way that is structured and supported. A key indicator of EKT pilot success is to evaluate if the procedures followed have enhanced the in-school placement experience in the area of cooperation and communication for the Student Teacher, university and the school in which the placement is taking place. The key roles at the school level include:

6.2.1. School Coordinator

In some countries, there will be a dedicated coordinator in each placement school who is the point of contact between the University and the school. Otherwise, this may be the Principal or staff member assigned as a single point of contact to liaise with the University in advance and during the school placement. The main tasks to be carried out by the School Coordinator include coordination, collaboration and communication with the other school placement participants via the EKT platform.

6.2.2. School Mentor

The School Mentor is the teacher in the placement school who supports and guides the Student Teacher and who is the point of contact between the University and the school. The School Mentor, in collaboration with the Academic Mentor, provides support in the form of constructive feedback.

- Participate in the EKT SPOC prior to the EKT Pilot commencement
- Work collaboratively with the Student Teacher, the Academic Mentor and the School Coordinator via the EKT platform
- Provide feedback to the Student Teacher through the EKT platform throughout the in-school placement

7. EKT PILOT TESTING PHASES

7.1. Pilot Preparation

The preparation phase for the EKT pilot comprises of a series of activities that need to be undertaken by the Academic Mentor, School Mentor and the Student Teacher and the University Coordinator. This phase takes place mainly at the University before the in-school placement begins. It is strongly connected with the preparation and delivery of the EKT online course (Small Private Online Course) which will introduce the Academic Mentors, School Mentors and Students to the EKT platform and methodology. At this stage the mentors will negotiate and agree on their strategy for collaboration, communication and monitoring of the Student Teacher. The Student Teacher will also be prepared for the pilot in the academic context.

7.1.1. Recruitment & selection of pilot participants

The recruitment of Student Teachers, University and School Mentors. Each pilot country will start contacting potential pilot groups well in advance of the planned start of the pilot. Depending on the way the placement process is organized in each country the recruitment can be done through the University Mentors or directly to a general cohort of student.

The pilot testing process may be advertised and explained in a brochure that will be translated into the pilot country languages.

Each EKT Pilot Coordinator will maintain an Excel spreadsheet with list of all Student Teachers, University and School Mentors taking part in the pilot testing process in their country. This spreadsheet will also help with creation of the participant accounts on the EKT platform.

7.1.2. Technical set up

All pilot participants need to have an account set up on the EKT app in line with their role in the school placement role. The platform functionality is depending on the user profile and the EKT app dashboard will also present different tools depending on the role of the user.

Information on how to create accounts for the pilot participants is provided in the help section of the EKT platform. Support and advice can also be received from CESGA technical team.

Once the user accounts are created, Student Teachers, Academic and/or School Coordinators should be registered to the EKT Online Course (SPOC) and the EKT Pilot Coordinator needs to ensure that the course is working for each participant.

7.1.3. Briefing meeting / onboarding

A meeting (online or face to face) for the pilot participants when they are introduced to the purpose of the SPOC and pilot, technical requirements, planned activities and timeframes. As each pilot is specific to the university there is no common guideline for this.

7.1.4. Training / Completion of SPOC

Completion of the EKT Online Course (SPOC) is considered as a preparatory stage to the EKT pilot however it may blend with the EKT Pilot activities. Ideally, the course should start 2 weeks before the in-school placement commencement.

7.1.5. Pre-pilot Evaluation

A number of evaluation instruments have been developed in order to gather the pilot participants' feedback and also measure the impact of the EKT platform and methodology has had on the target group. The first survey needs to be completed before the SPOC begins. Therefore the EKT Pilot Coordinator should provide the students with the link to the online questionnaire in advance of the SPOC and set a date for completion of the online questionnaire to coincide with the SPOC start date. Also a separate evaluation of the SPOC is embedded in the course itself.

7.2. Pilot Implementation Phase

The EKT methodology framework and EKT online platform is embedded into a school placement programme of the participating university taking into account the specific and formal requirement of the programme and the student cohort.

Pilot testing participants will explore the EKT platform features and functionality in the context of their school placement programme.

It will be mandatory for each pilot country to issue an ethical commitment with a consent for all participants.

University Coordinators / Academic Mentors should also monitor the activities on the platform, ensure that there is an ongoing participation and all issues and problems are resolved in due course.

7.3. Post Pilot Activities

The pilot testing evaluation process will be led by the Marino Institute of Education and Plymouth University, who will design, distribute, collect and analyse the evaluation questionnaires. The pilot testing evaluation report will be produced.

At the end of the pilot testing process the Student Teachers will receive a certificate of completion, in recognition of their participation and contribution to the EKT pilot.

8. SUPPORTS – WHO TO CONTACT

8.1. University Coordinators

- **Universidad de Santiago de Compostela** (Spain)

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8.2. EKT Platform

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8.3. EKT Online Course (SPOC)

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8.4. EKT Project Partners

8.4.1. Academic Partners

	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain) usc.es
Pädagogische Hochschule Wien	Pädagogische Hochschule Wien (Austria) phwien.ac.at
	Marino Institute of Education (Ireland) mie.ie
 Universidade do Minho	Universidade do Minho (Portugal) uminho.pt
UNIVERSITY OF PLYMOUTH	University of Plymouth (UK) plymouth.ac.uk

8.4.2. Technical Partners

BeezNest Solutions Open Source Efficaces	BeezNest (Belgium) beeznest.com
CESGA	Centro de Supercomputación de Galicia (Spain) cesga.gal
die Berater ZUKUNFT LERNEN	die Berater (Austria) dieberater.com
	H2 Learning (Ireland) h2learning.ie
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Tecnología Educativa (USC). <https://www.tecnoeduc.es/>